

BONDING STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES FOR AIRCRAFT

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ABSTRACT

Adhesive is a popular fastener for use in airframe composite structure. It is used for composite to composite, composite to metal, and of course, is indispensable for sandwich construction. In sandwich, it is used co-cured with the composite face skins, as well as for bonding precured face skins. A review of "state of the art" bonded composites shows a preponderance of carbon fibre materials. The reason for this is discussed together with descriptions of bonded structure. This leads to considerations of current problems with composite bonding and their suggested solutions. Among these problems are surface preparation for CRP, water migration through CRP sandwich skins, and galvanic destruction of metals (anodic) in conjunction with graphite composite (cathodic).

Keywords: Bonding, Adhesive, Carbon composite, Honeycomb, co-cured, interface, interleaf, galvanic, water migration.

1. CURRENT APPLICATIONS FOR BONDED COMPOSITES

In modern aircraft design there appears to be a preponderance of carbon fibre composites. Glass, Kevlar, and combinations of fibres are also used, but these do not generally equal carbon fibre for structural efficiency. The mechanical properties of carbon fibre result in superiority over the fibres and metals for specific strength, specific stiffness, and most recently, in performance at elevated temperature (in the range of supersonic flight) for commercial aircraft.

Adhesive bonding is clearly indispensable in honeycomb sandwich structure. Honeycomb panels with graphite faces are widely used to replace thin skin and stiffener construction. On the aircraft, these parts are control surfaces, (flaps, ailerons, speed brakes) and fairings. On airliners, these parts can be huge; up to 100 square feet is common. In general, these parts are acceptable, but certain problems prevent complete success. Chief of these is water intrusion through the composite skin. This happens due to permeability of the composite and sometimes

because of simple porosity.

A second problem is the tendency for thin skins to leave "mark off" for slight indentations over each cell. This is most common when the composite matrix resin is used as the adhesive, creating the bond when the face skins are cured on the core. "Mark off" can also occur when an adhesive is used during co-cure with the composite on the core. Bonding sandwich panels using pre-cured composite skins is not the most common procedure.

The presence of water in the honeycomb panel causes a variety of problems. Weight pick up can be serious. Water freezing can destroy the honeycomb cell structure. Water softens and weakens plastic core constructions such as nomex and fibre glass. This problem has many roots. Plastic core is used, in place of aluminum, for fear of galvanic destruction of the aluminum by the carbon fibres. Also, even though galvanic fears be overcome, there remains a concern about water degradation and corrosion of standard aluminum core. The question of water damage to aluminum honeycomb core is not always understood. It is often dealt with by the catch-all phrase of "honeycomb corrosion". This implies a destruction of the aluminum foil. This does happen, but a much more destructive phenomena happens first. This is the loss of the face bond to the aluminum foil. Figure 1 describes the details of bonding to the core of the honeycomb sandwich panel. The Achilles heel of standard core is the interface between the face bond adhesive and the honeycomb foil. This bond is often destroyed by moisture, and successive cells are opened up long before serious foil corrosion occurs. The integrity of the entire panel is usually lost before foil is destroyed. Solutions to these problems are presented in the second section of this paper.

We turn now from sandwich bonding to bonding composite to composite and to metal. Perhaps the most spectacular example of bonding composite to metal is that of the wing splice on the F-18 Fighter. Fig. 2 shows the schematic detail of this bonded joint. The wing bending materials are carbon fibre composite plates. These wing covers cannot be carried through the fuselage in one piece because of interference with the engine intake ducts and electronic equipment. The covers are bonded to titanium fitting using a stepped lap joint. The adhesive and the composite are co-cured against the titanium. This eliminates the problem of surface preparation of carbon fibre composites. To demonstrate the value of adhesive as a fastener, this wing joint would otherwise have required one thousand bolts. The cost and weight of bolts and holes in the composite can be seen to be enormous. This bonded attachment has shown no serious service problems over a span of nearly twenty years on hundreds of aircrafts.

Composite to composite bonds occur between stiffeners and skins on wings, stabilizers, and fins. In many cases these joints are not bonded with an adhesive. The matrix resin serves as the adhesive when the skin and stiffeners are both cured together in one operation. This procedure has worked on parts which are not highly stressed. However, very high shear concentrations can cause premature failure in the matrix "adhesive" between skin

and stiffener. Ref. 1 describes these shear concentrations as increased by stiffer adhesives and thin glue lines. Matrix resins are notorious for high modulus (stiff) and of course, are very very thin, less than the diameter of the carbon fibre. It can be shown that matrix stress concentrations can exceed those of a normal glue line by more than fifteen to one.

In many cases bonds are made between cured composite laminates. This procedure suffers from the serious problem of surface preparation for the cured laminates. This preparation is often done using "Peel Ply", a layer of cloth cured onto the laminate and then peeled off to present a bondable surface. The bonds thus obtained are known to be erratic, yet the method remains popular. This is largely because the next logical method, surface abrasion, is very unpopular because of the possibility of fibre damage. Many designs involve curing composite against an already cured composite, with or without an adhesive. These methods eliminate the surface preparation problem for one surface, but not for the other.

2. FUTURE COMPOSITE BONDING AND SOLUTIONS TO CURRENT PROBLEMS

In sandwich construction, two very useful solutions to water ingestion are just appearing. The first is a moisture barrier included in the adhesive in the form of a carrier of thin film of thermoplastic. Bond durability to the film under wet conditions has been obtained. Water entry is excluded from porosity and permeability of the skin. Also, the film stiffness acts as a bridge over the core cells and eliminates mark-off. The second solution involves a major improvement in aluminum honeycomb core with the advent of PAA Core. This core has extraordinary resistance to moisture, water, and corrosion. The foil is phosphoric acid anodized and coated with corrosion resistant primer. This is arguably the best aluminum surface preparation yet developed for durability in hot-wet environment. Failure of the bond of the face adhesive to the core foil interface has been virtually eliminated. This means water cannot enter except by corroding the wall of the first cell. The primer virtually eliminates this. Galvanic corrosion has been obviated, since water (electrolyte) cannot contact both the aluminum and graphite. This opens the way towards stronger, stiffer, and cheaper core for graphite faced honeycomb panels.

In the case of bonding composite to composite or composite to metal, the problems are 1) composite surface preparation, and, 2) avoiding thin glue lines. The best surface preparation remains abrasion, and the problem is to avoid fibre damage. We know of programs involving extreme care and strict procedural controls. These can work, but another procedure is to co-cure a layer of adhesive on the surfaces to be subsequently bonded. This surface can then be abraded, with no danger of fibre damage, and the final bond can be made to an ideal surface.

The thin glue line problem is eliminated on the F-18 wing splice by heat aging the adhesive slightly while in contact with the titanium. This reduces the flow of the adhesive and results in a thick glue line with no mixing or blending into the co-cured matrix resin of the graphite composite. Another solution has

been developed to avoid thin glue lines and/or avoid blending of the adhesive into the matrix resin. This is an adhesive in "interleaf" form. This means a minor change in any well established formulation in order to reduce the flow. The result is no blending and a thick, discrete glue line in all combinations of cured and co-cured composites. These interleaf adhesives also bond very well to metals.

The future of composite bonding is bright. The day must come when the price of holes for mechanical fasteners will be seen too high. The very nature of a composite is its fibrousness. This compromises bearing strength and makes interlaminar stress concentrations critical. The comparison to wood is irresistible. The beginning of this century saw aircraft made of bonded fibrous structure, glued wood. The end of this century will see aircraft made of bonded fibrous structure, man-made composite.

References

1. Evaluating Structural Adhesives Under Sustained Load in Hostile Environment. Oct. (1973), SAMPE Conference, American Cyanamid Company

FIGURE 1. Pictorial Description of Face Bonds and Node Bonds to Honeycomb Core

FIGURE 2. F-18 Wing to Fuselage Bonded Attachment, Schematic